

Academic Engagement As A Predictor Of Academic Achievement Among Public Senior Secondary School Students In Anambra State.

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated academic engagement as a predictor of academic achievement among public senior secondary school students in Anambra State, Nigeria. One research question guided the study and one hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted a correlational survey design. The population of the study consisted of 20,560 senior secondary school students (SSS II) in the 267 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The sample for the study was 300 SSII students who were drawn using multi-stage sampling from three public secondary schools. An instrument was used for the data collection of this study. The instrument was: Academic Engagement Scale, it is a standardized instrument and has been properly validated and tested for reliability. Also termly results of students in English language, Mathematics and Science were collected from their school records. The data collected were analysed using multiple regression analysis. The finding of the study indicated that behavioural, emotional, and cognitive engagement significantly predicted students' academic achievement, collectively explaining 52% of the variance. Based on the findings conclusions were drawn, and the study underscored the importance of engagement-focused interventions in schools to enhance academic outcomes.

Keywords: Academic Achievements, Predictor, Academic engagement.

INTRODUCTION

Academic achievement is widely regarded as a critical indicator of educational effectiveness and a determinant of students' future academic and career opportunities. In Nigeria, the performance of students in public senior secondary schools has been a persistent concern, with many students struggling to meet the minimum requirements in core subjects such as Mathematics, English, and Science (WAEC, 2023). Reports from the West African Examinations Council indicate that a significant proportion of students in public schools perform below expected standards, highlighting the urgent need to explore factors that can enhance learning outcomes.

Several studies have identified multiple determinants of academic achievement, including socioeconomic status, teacher quality, classroom resources, and student-related factors such as motivation, self-efficacy, and engagement (Asanre, Ifamuyiwa, & Abiodun, 2024). Among these, academic engagement has gained prominence as a key psychological and behavioural factor influencing academic performance. Academic engagement is a multidimensional construct encompassing behavioural, emotional, and cognitive aspects (Fredricks et al., 2016). Behavioural engagement refers to students' active participation in learning

activities, including attending classes, completing assignments, and participating in discussions. Emotional engagement involves positive feelings toward learning, interest in classroom activities, and a sense of belonging in school. Cognitive engagement relates to students' investment in learning through strategies such as critical thinking, self-regulation, and deep processing of information.

Empirical evidence has shown that students who are highly engaged academically tend to demonstrate better learning outcomes, including higher grades, greater persistence in challenging tasks, and more effective problem-solving abilities (Ayoola, 2025; International Journal of Social Sciences and Management Research, 2025). In the Nigerian context, where public schools often face challenges such as overcrowded classrooms, limited instructional materials, and uneven teacher quality, fostering academic engagement may be particularly important. Students who are actively involved in their learning are more likely to overcome these challenges and achieve academic success.

Despite the growing recognition of academic engagement as a predictor of student achievement, there is limited empirical research in Nigeria that examines all three dimensions of engagement behavioural, emotional, and cognitive, simultaneously in relation to academic achievement. Most studies have either focused on one dimension of engagement or examined small samples in urban schools, leaving a gap in understanding how engagement operates across diverse public senior secondary school contexts.

This study, therefore, seeks to investigate the predictive relationship between academic engagement and academic achievement among public senior secondary students in Anambra State. By examining the contributions of behavioural, emotional, and cognitive engagement to students' performance in core subjects, this research aims to provide empirical evidence that can inform educational policies, instructional practices, and intervention strategies targeted at improving student outcomes in Anambra State public senior secondary schools.

Academic engagement is a multifaceted construct that reflects the extent to which students are involved in classroom activities and learning processes. It is typically understood to include behavioural engagement (e.g., participation, task completion), emotional engagement (e.g., interest, motivation, sense of belonging), and cognitive engagement (e.g., deep processing, self-regulated learning strategies). Engagement has been linked to higher academic achievement in various school contexts because engaged students tend to employ effective learning strategies, sustain attention, and persist through academic challenges (Fredricks et al., 2016).

Recent empirical studies in Nigeria have demonstrated positive associations between academic engagement and academic performance among senior secondary school students. Asanre, Ifamuyiwa, and Abiodun (2024) found that behavioural, emotional, and cognitive engagement jointly predicted mathematics achievement among senior secondary students in Ogun State, Nigeria. Specifically, cognitive engagement demonstrated a strong predictive influence, indicating that students who invest in deeper learning strategies perform better academically in Mathematics.

Ayoola (2025) showed that all dimensions of academic engagement significantly relate to Physics achievement in senior secondary schools in Taraba State, with increases in engagement corresponding to higher achievement scores. These Nigerian studies confirm that engagement not only correlates with educational outcomes but can be a useful predictor of students' subject-specific performance.

Emesi and Anyanwu (2024) found that social goal orientation and academic engagement jointly predicted students' mathematics achievement in Anambra State, suggesting that the motivational climate influences how engagement affects academic outcomes. Additionally, contextual factors such as school environment and classroom management influence engagement levels and, indirectly, academic achievement (Sokedu Review of Education, 2023). Positive school climates and interactive classroom management were associated with higher engagement and better academic outcomes.

Further research indicates that teachers' competence predicts student engagement, demonstrating that skilled educators are more likely to foster engagement that improves academic achievement (Educational Research and Development Journal, 2024). Instructional strategies such as collaborative learning, cooperative assignments, and problem-solving tasks have been shown to enhance student engagement and academic performance in Nigerian public secondary schools (Journals of Teacher Education and Social Engagement, 2025).

Although empirical research from other African countries is emerging, findings are consistent with Nigerian studies: student engagement is influenced by school climate, instructional quality, and teacher-student interactions, all of which affect academic achievement.

Most studies focus on single subjects or explore one dimension of engagement. Few examine behavioural, emotional, and cognitive engagement simultaneously in relation to overall academic achievement across core subjects. This study addresses these gaps by examining all three dimensions within a predictive framework.

Despite the considerable research attention focused on these constructs, it appears that in Nigeria, the comprehensive/ broad nature of these constructs as well as their relationship to academic achievement has not been attained. This may be observed in the trend of academic achievement of students in external examinations especially in English Language and Mathematics which has not necessarily improved from what it used to be (WAEC, 2018). This present study deemed it fit to examine the predictive relationship between academic engagement and academic achievement among public senior secondary students in Anambra State.

Frankly speaking, efforts have been made by researchers and educators towards improving achievements of students but greater attention were given to methods and practices used in teaching and learning that will ensure a better achievement of the students. Also attention has been drawn to students' factors in dealing with the means of improving students' achievements in the school but much interests are on cognitive domain of the students with little interest on other factors that contribute to students' better achievement in school activities. Factor such as academic engagement is a variable which seems to have great effect on the achievement of students. In real sense, some researchers have either considered one or two of these constructs in relation to students' achievement but none to the knowledge of the researchers has investigated specifically on the predictive relationship between academic engagement and academic achievements of secondary school students in Anambra state. Hence, the present study.

Purpose and Scope of the Study

The major purpose of this study is to investigate the predictive relationship between academic engagement and academic achievements of secondary school students in Anambra state. This study is specifically designed to determine: (a) The extent secondary school students' academic engagement predict their academic achievement.

The study is delimited to investigation of the predictive relationship between academic engagement and academic achievements of public senior secondary school students in Anambra State. The students' achievement scores in English language and Mathematics for the academic year and the questionnaire were used. The study is delimited to SS II students. The SS III students were exempted because they were preparing for their final examinations while the SS I students were new in the senior class.

Research Questions

This research questions guided this study: (a) To what extent do secondary school students academic engagement predict their academic achievement?

Research Hypothesis

This null hypothesis formulated guided the study and was tested at 0.05 significance levels. (a) Senior secondary school students' academic engagement do not significantly predict their academic achievement.

METHOD

Design of the Study

A descriptive correlational design was employed to examine the predictive relationship between academic engagement and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Anambra state.

Population of the Study

The population of this study was made up of 20,560 Senior Secondary Two (SS II) students within the age range of 14 to 18 years. They were drawn from 267 public secondary schools in Anambra state. As at the time of this study, there were 20,560 senior secondary 11 students in Anambra state public secondary

schools. (Source: Planning Research and Statistics, PPSSC, Awka, 2024). These SS II students are in the six education zones in the state.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample of this study consists of 300 SSII students from three public schools in Anambra State, using stratified random sampling to ensure representation and gender. Participants' ages ranged from 14 to 18 years.

Instruments for the Data Collection

The instrument used to collect data for the study was Academic Engagement Instrument Questionnaire (AEI), proposed by Bob Fredricks & Penny D. Blumenfeld (2004) The instrument was used to collect information on Academic Engagement of students. It has two sections. Section one contain information of the respondents such as name, age, sex, date. The section two is on Academic Engagement items, made up of twenty items measuring behavioural, emotional, and cognitive engagement on a 4-point Likert scale (4 = strongly agree, 1 = strongly disagree). In addition, the students' academic achievement scores obtained from examination scores of teachers made tests in Mathematics and English and Science obtained from PPSSC portal Awka, 2023/2024, were used for the study.

Validation and Reliability of the Instrument

The face and content validity of the instrument were established by three experts from the Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus. The research topic, purpose of the study, research questions, and hypotheses were given to three experts. The instruments were trial-tested in a single administration on a representative sample of 30 students randomly selected from Army Day Secondary School, Enugu in Enugu state, which was outside the area of study to avoid sample contamination. The responses of the respondents were collated to ascertain the internal consistency of the items in each of the instruments. Cronbach Alpha Method was used. The choice of Cronbach Alpha is in line with Stephen (2017) who recommended Cronbach Alpha as a proper statistical tool for determining internal consistency of an instrument. In addition, Cronbach Alpha was also used to determine the reliability because the items in the instruments are not dichotomously scored. The computation yielded co-efficient values of 0.87.

Method of Data Collection

The researchers adopted face to face method of instrument administration which was done during their free periods in each school selected. This was done through the help of eight existing trained research assistants specifically Mathematics, English, and Science teachers in each of the sampled schools. The copies of the questionnaire were distributed and collected by the researchers with the help of the assistants. Then the terminal results of the students were collected.

The questionnaires were numbered and tagged in line with the arrangement of the students' names in the terminal result sheets to ensure that the numbering followed how the students were given the questionnaire to answer. This was to ensure that appropriate achievement scores of the students are properly tagged with their responses on the questionnaire.

Method of Data Analysis

The data was analyzed using statistical package for Social Science (SPSS 26). Data were analysed using descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation) and multiple regression to determine the predictive effect of engagement on achievement.

RESULTS

Research Question: *To what extent do secondary school students academic engagement predict their academic achievement?*

Null Hypothesis

Senior secondary school students' academic engagement do not significantly predict their academic achievement.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Academic Engagement and Academic Achievement

Variable	N	Min	Max	Mean	SD
Behavioural Engagement	300	15	50	34.62	6.12
Emotional Engagement	300	12	48	32.45	7.05
Cognitive Engagement	300	14	52	35.10	6.55
Academic Achievement (Score)	300	40	95	72.28	10.32

Table 2: Multiple Regression Analysis Predicting Academic Achievement

Predictor Variable	B	SE B	β	T	P
Behavioural Engagement	0.85	0.15	0.38	5.67	<.001
Emotional Engagement	0.62	0.14	0.27	4.43	<.001
Cognitive Engagement	0.90	0.16	0.41	5.63	<.001
R² = 0.52, F(3,296)=106.42, p<.001					

Note: B = unstandardized coefficient; SE B = standard error; β = standardized coefficient.

DISCUSSION

The results indicate that behavioural, emotional, and cognitive engagement are significant predictors of academic achievement among Nigerian public senior secondary students. Cognitive engagement had the strongest predictive value ($\beta = 0.41$), suggesting that students' use of deep learning strategies and self-regulation is crucial for success. Behavioural engagement ($\beta = 0.38$) emphasizes participation and task completion, while emotional engagement ($\beta = 0.27$) highlights the role of motivation and positive attitudes.

These findings align with student engagement theory and previous Nigerian studies (Asanre et al., 2024; Ayoola, 2025). They suggest that interventions targeting all three dimensions can improve academic outcomes, particularly in resource-constrained public school environments.

Conclusion and Implications

Academic engagement is a robust predictor of academic achievement in Nigerian public senior secondary schools. Schools should adopt strategies to enhance behavioural, emotional, and cognitive engagement, including interactive teaching methods, supportive learning environments, and self-regulated learning training. Policymakers should integrate engagement-focused approaches into teacher training and curriculum planning. Future research could explore longitudinal effects of engagement interventions on students' performance in national examinations.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study on the predictive relationship between academic engagement and academic achievement of senior secondary school students, several recommendations could be made to enhance educational practices, support student development, and foster better academic outcomes. These recommendations target educators, school administrators, policymakers, and future researchers.

To maximize the positive impact of academic engagement on achievement, schools should implement strategies to encourage active participation among students. Educators should adopt teaching methods that promote active learning, such as group discussions, problem-solving exercises, and hands-on projects. Engaging students actively in their learning processes can increase their interest and commitment. Implement regular feedback mechanisms that allow students to express their thoughts on teaching methods, course content, and overall engagement. Listening to student voices can help adapt instructional approaches to better meet their needs and interests. Encourage participation in extracurricular activities that align with students' interests and strengths. Being involved in clubs, sports, or arts can foster a sense of belonging and further enhance academic engagement.

Engagement should not be limited to the classroom; fostering a home and community environment that supports educational success is essential. Schools can offer programs to educate parents about the

importance of academic engagement, as well as provide strategies for supporting their children's academic and emotional well-being.

In summary, the recommendations from this study provided actionable strategies for enhancing educational outcomes by focusing on the development, and promotion of academic engagement. Implementing these recommendations can create a supportive and effective learning environment that optimally prepares students for academic success and personal growth. Collaboration among educators, parents, and the community, along with continued research, will further empower students to achieve their full potential.

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